

A Review on Effective Strategies for Teaching English Pronunciation to EFL Learners (Literature Review)

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Abstract

Pronunciation is the basic component of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning, as it significantly influences learners' intelligibility, comprehensibility, and overall communicative competence. In traditional language classrooms, pronunciation instruction is neglected by the instructors, and the traditional instructors place more emphasis on reading, grammar, vocabulary, and writing skills. This literature review examines effective strategies for teaching English pronunciation to EFL learners, drawing on previous research and theoretical perspectives. The study highlights a range of instructional techniques, including tongue twister activities, minimal pairs practice, listening-based instruction, phonetic training, and the teaching of rhythm and stress patterns. It also emphasizes the importance of communicative pronunciation teaching and learner-centered approaches that focus on meaningful interaction and awareness of phonological features. The review indicates that integrating systematic pronunciation instruction into language teaching can enhance learners' oral performance, accuracy, and confidence in spoken communication. Overall, the study concludes that effective pronunciation teaching requires a combination of explicit instruction, practice-based activities, and exposure to authentic language input.

Keywords: *Pronunciation, activities, strategies, instructions, comprehending, intelligibility.*

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Introduction

Pronunciation is the individual sounds within a language, and pronunciation includes word stress, sentence stress, intonation, and word linking. One of the key elements of language learning is pronunciation. When we want to learn a language, it is important to have an understandable knowledge of the pronunciation of that language; speaking and comprehending the language may be difficult for us. Communication or proper discussion in a second language depends on a good knowledge of pronunciation. However, we understand a lot of words or lexicon in a language, but if we have a lot of problems in pronunciation, we may not be able to comprehend our speech to our interlocutor.

In the previous most of the teachers tried just on the learning of reading, writing, speaking and vocabulary, and there was not any attention for teaching and learning of the pronunciation, although it was and L2 learners need to know and have a good pronunciation skill while they want to learning English as the second language, because between Dari and English there is a big

difference in pronunciation of words, sentence stress and all the letters of Dari is different from English language.

As we know that the English language is an international language, we should learn and teach its pronunciation continuously with the other skills of the language. So it is necessary to know the methods and approaches for teaching pronunciation. In this article, I will discuss the issues that help second language learners to comprehend how they learn the pronunciation of English language.

As stated by Burns (2003), and cited by Lahijan, (2012), for speakers of English it is important to know the following issues:

- 1 Intelligibility (the speaker produces sound patterns that are recognizable as English) (Gilakjani, 2012)
- 2 Comprehensibility (the listener is able to understand the meaning of what is said) (Gilakjani, 2012)
- 3 Interpretability (the listener is able to understand the purpose of what is what is said) (Gilakjani, 2012)

For example, a speaker might say *It's hot today* as *IS ho day*. This is unlikely to be intelligible because of inaccurate sound, stress and intonation patterns. As a result, a listener would not find the speaker comprehensible, because meaning is not available. Because the speaker is incomprehensible, the listener would also not be able to interpret the utterance as an indirect request to open the window stated by Burns (2003), and cited by Lahijan (2012) (Gilakjani, 2012).

To know and solve the mentioned problems it is necessary to understand the best ways to help the learners in order to have a good and accurate pronunciation. As a result, in this chapter I do a literature review and I hope it will be beneficial for the students and teachers of the English language.

My goal for teaching pronunciation is to enhance the knowledge of the students in pronunciation by using different strategies and methods, to help the students and show them that pronunciation is as important as the other skills of the language, and to prepare them with the materials for making good pronunciation. As a result, in this article, I want to use the tongue twister technique, the minimal pairs technique, listening for improving pronunciation, teaching English rhythm and stress, and phonetics training to improve the pronunciation of my students.

Definition of Pronunciation Strategy

As stated by Murat (2012), the strategy of pronunciation is the deliberate, conduct and idea which is used by the assimilators to permit them learn, comprehend and recall the L2 pronunciation. Also stated that a pronunciation strategy is an effort to increase phonetic and phonological capability in the target language.

As stated by Pawlak (2010), pronunciation strategy is careful ideas and actions that intentionally take place in a logical sequence, for study and receiving great control over the use of various aspects of pronunciation.

Cook (1996, as cited in Pourhosein Gilakjani, 2016) said that pronunciation is the production of English sounds Izzati, N. (2019) Izzati, N. (2019). When the words are produced inaccurately, we can correct them by repeating and making the pronunciation correct by repeating. While the learners start learning a new language, they make new habits and succeed in their first language. As Richard and Schmidt (2002) defined, pronunciation is the method of producing certain sounds.

Rasuli & Mobarakzada (2023), stated that that widely the term pronunciation is a creation of notable sound in to two senses; first sound is essential since it is used as a part of the code of particular language. In this purpose, it is place that it is necessary to say something about classifiable sound in English, French this and other languages. Second, sound is essential to be use for attaining meaning in the context of use. As Richard & Schmidt (2023) state, pronunciation is a way of producing inevitable sounds.

Strategies for Solving Problems in Pronunciation

As stated by Burns (2003), and cited by Lahijan (2012), strategies that assist learners to solve their problems in English pronunciation are:

- Identify specific pronunciation features that cause problems for learners (Gilakjani, 2012)
- Make learners aware of the prosodic features of language (stress, intonation, rhythm) (Gilakjani, 2012)
- Focus on developing learners' communicative competence (Gilakjani, 2012)

As I comprehend if the learners identify the specific pronunciation features they can solve their problems in pronunciation, and for identifying the feature of pronunciation, he suggested contrastive analysis, by contrasting the features of two languages, the learners can easily anticipate or know the problems which will they face to (Burns (2003), and cited by Lahijan Branch, (2012).

As stated by Ali and Souzandehfar (2011), in most languages the letters symbolize one phoneme in spelling, while in the English language it is not the same. As an example, the two letters “ch” represent the single phoneme (ʃ), however the letters “k” and “c” symbolize one phoneme /k/ as in kind and can. Some letters like “g” has produce two phonemes like /g/ as in gun and /j/ as in gym, but in Persian we don't have these kinds of sounds that we have letters like / چ / in all cases, this phoneme is pronounced as/j/. Also, he stated that the mother language influences the effects on teaching the English language too.

As stated by Peterson (2000), pronunciation for learning strategies are twelve, that are symbolize sounds in memory, train naturalistically, official train with sounds, analyzed the sound system, nearest articulations, discovery of the aimed language pronunciation, arranging goals and objectives, intending for a language task, self-assessment, using comedy to decrease anxiety, requesting for help, assisting with co-workers, and symbolizing sounds in memory (Hişmanoğlu, 2012).

There are two major pronunciation learning strategies: self-correction of poor pronunciation and active listening to native pronunciation (Vitonava & Miller, 2002; Hişmanoğlu, 2012).

Morley (1991) stated that one of the aims of teaching pronunciation is intelligible pronunciation, which is a crucial part of communicative competence. The accomplishment of ideal pronunciation should not be the aim. Morley offered the more realistic aims, which are reasonable, applicable, and suitable for the communication needs of the learners (Gilakjani, 2012).

Rajadurai (2001) suggested that if the students or learners of the L2 want to learn pronunciation properly, they should participate in the listening and speaking courses.

Strategies for English Pronunciation Instruction

As stated by Lahijan (2012), there are three strategies for English pronunciation instruction that help the learners to overcome their problems on pronunciation problems:

- a Identify specific pronunciation features that cause problems for learners
- b Make learners aware of the prosodic features of language (stress, intonation, rhythm)
- c Focus on developing learners' communicative competence

According to Rubin (1975), good language learners use a set of learning strategies. For instance, they practice word pronunciation, want to find time to speak with native speakers to learn good pronunciation, observe their speech, and place suitable intonation on individual sounds. All of the mentioned processes are pronunciation strategies (Licensee, 2015).

Gilakjani (2016), the aim of pronunciation instruction is that we should not pronounce like the native speakers. The real purpose should be intelligible pronunciation for oral communication. Whether the learners need to alter the manner of pronouncing the English words, it would be better to alter the manner they want they deem about the sounds of those words. Pronunciation instruction is sometimes neglected by speakers (Pourhosein Gilakjani, 2011; Pourhosein Gilakjani, 2016).

According to James (2010), these levels are the goals for pronunciation instruction:

- 1 The speaker's speech is not comprehensible to people. When the speakers produce the sounds, they use incorrect sounds. According to Hinofotis and Bailey (1980, as cited in Celce-Murcia & Goodwin, 1991), there is a primary level for pronunciation.
- 2 The speaker is comprehensible to people, but the speaker's pronunciation is not acceptable to listen to because of an unusual accent. Morley (1994) stated that when a speaker's pronunciation is laboriously accented, it can have an effect on the speaker's understanding.
- 3 The speaker's English is acceptable to listen to because people comprehend it. Scovel (1988) called it pleasant intelligibility, and it should be the aim of English pronunciation.
- 4 As Morley (1991) stated, the role of the teacher in English pronunciation instruction is as a facilitator for learning pronunciation.
- 5 As stated by Shahzada (2012), for improving English pronunciation instruction, there are some suggestions for EFL learners to assist them in improving their English pronunciation. EFL instructors should train accurately in pronunciation to develop their learners' English pronunciation. EFL instructors must speak clearly and gradually in their pronunciation classes, and they should persuade their learners that their language is comprehensible. This will help learners develop their pronunciation by listening carefully (Bradley-Bennett, 2007).

Jack & Willy (2002) stated that teaching pronunciation is changeable over time. To produce individual accurate sounds, we should concentrate more wider to communicative aspects for connecting speech

Another strategy that will be very interesting and helpful for students who want to learn pronunciation better is a mobile application. As stated by Cavus (2016), mobile application also can be used in language learning, mainly in teaching English pronunciation. In his research he learned that this application has a speech recognition engine which help mobile phone to comprehend the spoken words, and every pronunciation problem can undoubtedly be cleared and then treated. It will help the learners to motivate and make the learning easy and more entertaining than the classic learning methods (Cavus, 2016).

As stated by Robin, (2015), other ways which can improve pronunciation is making portfolio, the components which will include in the portfolio are; audio or video records of oral task. In this procedure, repetition of drill, creation of minimal pairs, reading in a loud mode and role play and

oral presentation is very helpful. Many other strategies like; written or recorded reflection, written and recorded self-assessment and record of improved versions also suggested by the above writer.

Teaching Pronunciation

Pronunciation is one of the important skills for learning a second or foreign language. Knowing pronunciation in language help the learners to distinguish the words and have good communication. According to Gilakjani (2012), pronunciation is an integral part for learning a foreign language since it directly affects learners' communicative competence as well as performance. According to Elliot as cited by Gilakjani (2016), pronunciation is one of the most important features of an individual's speech, but most of the teachers do not have attention to teach and work with their students to improve their pronunciation. Also he stated that when we want to learn English language pronunciation should teach equally with the other skills such; grammar, reading, writing, speaking, and listening. As stated by Albiladii 2019, one of the skills which the EFL learners do not pay attention to is the pronunciation skill; both learners and teachers have problems in learning the pronunciation skill.

In my opinion EFL learners will face to many problems if they do not pay their attention for learning the pronunciation of English, because English is a very complicated language according its nature, for example the word which write in the way it is not pronounce as it has written like “abbreviation” although the compound letter of “tion” is like “shan” but in this word it pronounces like “zhan”. Like this, there is a lot of problems for the learners. As result it is the duty of all the teachers to teach pronunciation for their student's parallel with the other skills of the language.

The tongue twister technique goal is to strengthen the English sounds that students have learned by creating a game like atmosphere for practice. As stated by Rohman (2016), tongue twister is a sentence or phrase that is indented to be difficult to say, when it is repeated quickly and often. It is wise to include tongue twister that highlight particularly problematic minimal sound differences (e.g., pronunciation of /f/ and /v/; /s/ and /š/; /f/ and /θ/) (Rohman, 2016). Tongue twister is very interesting because they are consisting of many similar sounds usually they are different in written and meaning form, as in “Kantai can tie a tie. If Kantai can tie a tie, why can't I tie a tie like Kantai can tie a tie.” (Rohman, 2016). Or we can say the sentence like, “can you can the can.” These are the sentences that make a challenge in pronunciation of the learners, but help them to make a fluent and good pronunciation. As stated by Rohman (2016), there are three types of tongue twister; the first one is sentence type like; six sleek swans swam swiftly southwards. A big black bug bit a big black dog on his big black nose! The next type is Repetitive type like; Sheena leads, Sheila needs, World Wide Web, Babbling bumbling band of baboons. The third one is a story type, like when you write copy, you have the right to copyright the copy you write. You can write good and copyright, but copyright doesn't mean copy good – it might not be right good copy, right?

Tongue twisters have various levels of difficulty. So that, a teacher should select an appropriate type of tongue twister based on the age and ability of his or her students. In this research, the researcher had used all the above types using various techniques. Even though the third type is a very long tongue twister, it could be effectively applied by using “one by one reading” technique.

The second technique which I discuss here, is using minimal pairs. My goal is to distinguish minimal pairs in form of the sentences, so I use minimal pair strategy. I will apply this strategy through communicative approach to show that there is a threshold level of pronunciation for nonnative speakers of English through this approach. According to Marcia and Grinder (2010), minimal pair is a technique which was introduced during the audio-lingual era to help students distinguish between similar and problematic sounds in the target language through listening discrimination and

listening practice. Usually, minimal pair's exercises begin with word level drills and end with sentence level drills. Also, minimal pairs are very effective tools for language teachers. They help the teachers to learn unfamiliar phonemes. Because the perception of phoneme is needed before pronunciation can occur, minimal pairs can also help students when they are ready to speak. Teachers should know in what minimal pairs their students have problem. When the teachers teach their students they should write down the words which are mispronounced by their students. After that, they should make a list of the sounds and give practice to the students in the form of words and sentences.

I use various activities and games while I teach minimal pairs. For example, I use vocabulary- grab game. In this game, Students work in groups of 3-4. I put a few minimal pair words on slips of paper (one word per paper) and give a set to each group. Then call out a word. The students race to grab the correct word. Keep calling until there's none left - the winner has the most words (Henderson, & Carter, 2018; Sato, & Kim, 2020). Then get the students working within their groups. One student calls out the words, the others grab the word he/she said. Finally, I encourage lots of competition to keep them motivated. The other activity which I use is shouting dictation. It is a bit noisy, but great to get students exaggerating the mouth shapes (Henderson, & Carter, 2018; Sato, & Kim, 2020). Students work in pairs. Each student has a different set of words which they must dictate to their partner. However, they must stand on opposite sides of the room, so they have to shout. Play background music to make it even more challenging. And finally, minimal pair bingo is the most interesting game which I play with my students. Most of the students are eager for this game (Henderson, & Carter, 2018; Sato, & Kim, 2020). I found it funny among the students. Lots of students love it. In this game, basically, students choose 9 words from the minimal pairs you give and write them in a 3*3 square. You call out the words and they tick them off as they come up. If they think you've said all the words, they shout "Bingo!" (Henderson, & Carter, 2018; Sato, & Kim, 2020).

The third strategy which I want to teach to improve my students' pronunciation is the listening. According to Albiladi (2019), one of the most important way for improving EFL students' pronunciation is the listening. Teachers should let the students to listen to native speakers. As a teacher I should the students to listen to native speakers of English language to know how the native speakers pronounce a word. The first way students should listen and identify the sounds. After identifying the sounds, I will let them to listen to news, TV, radio and any other sources, to recognize how each letters, words and sentences are pronounced by the native speakers. This will lead to better and more intelligible pronunciation.

The next technique which I would like to implement in my class is phonetics training. I believe teaching phonetics symbols can improve my students' pronunciation and they are useful tools for learning correct pronunciation. According to Morley (as cited in Reid 2016), this technique is quite demanding as it includes phonetically transcribed words or texts. Students need to learn phonetic symbols. They should know the vowels and consonants sounds which are forty-four sounds. They should also know how to connect them to the individual sounds. For implementing this technique, I use visual aids such as phonetics charts, articulatory diagrams and videos that contain pronunciation from native speakers. I use this technique to help my students overcome their pronunciation problems. This technique is not suitable for young and beginner learners. Because, it is difficult for young learners to learn the forty-four sounds in phonetic alphabet. Even though, it is helpful for adult learners. Adults have difficulties to hear different sounds and imitate them. When it is explicitly explained how sounds are produced and they are given concrete visual form of a symbol. It is a helpful device for adult learner to understand and pronounce the different sounds. I do agree with the author and I believe that language instructors can use this technique to help their students learn pronunciation well. I suggest that this should be used for advanced level

students because it will be difficult and challenging for lower level students to learn phonetics symbols which are very complicated. It is correct that by using the phonetics symbols students can learn to produce sounds accurately and it is possible that they will be able to pronounce like native speakers.

The last issue which I want to teach the pronunciation for my learners is the teaching English rhythm and stress. As stated by Moriya and cited in Albiladii (2019), EFL learners have problem on pronunciation because of the rhythm. As stated by Chen and cited in Albiladii (2019), rhythm is a timing patterns on syllables, and timing pattern is different in all languages, and rhythm is divided in to two categories in a language: first one is stress-timed and the second is syllable timed. For example, English is stress-timed, while many other languages such as Arabic and most Asian languages, with nearly equal weight and time in all syllables, is syllable-timed (stated by Flege, & Robert, and cited in Albiladii 2019). Significantly, English words are divided into two groups: English content words such as main verbs, nouns, adjectives, and question words. These words are usually stressed. On the other hand, function words such as articles and prepositions are usually unstressed (as stated by Gilakjani, and cited in Albiladii 2019).

However, there are many effective steps EFL teachers can take to help students understand English rhythms and stresses. First, when teaching a new word, the teachers also need to teach its stress pattern. The teachers can emphasize stressed syllables using various visual effects. Second, EFL teachers might ask students to predict stress in words. Third, teachers can provide students with charts that explain the differences between stressed and unstressed syllables. Some charts help students understand how stressed syllables differ from unstressed ones in terms of three features: loudness, length, and pitch. Knowing the differences will help them acquire the correct rhythm. Finally, students can learn stress patterns in English by saying English rhymes. To say an English rhyme, students must stress certain words and weaken others. It helps students learn the language's natural rhythm. Overall, EFL teachers must be aware of the importance of teaching English rhythm to EFL students. Since many EFL students tend to use their first language rhythm in their English speech, many educators believe that teaching English rhythm (stress-timed) to EFL students is well worth the effort. EFL teachers have to spend some time working on English rhythms, besides individual sounds. By teaching English rhythm, teachers may see surprising progress in their students' English pronunciation.

To assess students' progress in learning pronunciation and accurate pronunciation of words and sounds in English language, I prefer to use formative assessment in teaching classrooms. I have experienced teaching pronunciation before, and I tried to make my students repeat the words and sounds accurately after tape recorder and I was closely monitoring their progress. Besides that, I will try to check whether my students accurately and correctly pronounce the words after I teach. I believe teachers need to repeat practicing it because if students do not repeat it, they will forget it. Or, it is also possible that students might have forgotten the accurate pronunciation and they might pronounce it inaccurately. To assess students' comprehension of reduced forms through listen and repeat, I will use weekly quizzes and final achievement test, I will play an audio or video in which the native speakers use reduced forms and I will stop the audio after each sentence and ask my students to write what they have heard. I will use the paper and evaluate how successfully they have done it.

In conclusion, pronunciation is as important as the other skills of the language. So all teachers should try to teach pronunciation in parallel with other skills like reading, writing, grammar, listening, speaking, and pronunciation. Knowing the pronunciation helps the EFL learners to verify different words and improve communication. Teachers should use different strategies for teaching pronunciation. The strategies and techniques that help students learn pronunciation include listening to the radio and TV, learning phonemic sounds of words, and understanding the rhythm

and stress in a language. In the past, the teachers did not have attention to teaching pronunciation. The strategies which I mentioned are very useful for EFL teachers and can be taught in all contexts especially in Afghanistan, where most teachers and learners have problems on teaching pronunciation.

Results

Based on the reviewed literature on effective strategies for teaching English pronunciation to EFL learners, several key findings emerge. The analysis of previous studies indicates that pronunciation instruction is essential for developing learners' communicative competence, particularly in improving intelligibility and comprehensibility in spoken English.

First, the literature consistently shows that **explicit pronunciation instruction is more effective than implicit learning alone**. Techniques such as minimal pairs, phonetic training, and focused listening activities help learners become more aware of sound differences and reduce interference from their first language.

Second, **interactive and engaging classroom activities**, such as tongue twisters, games, and communicative drills, significantly increase learners' motivation and participation, leading to better pronunciation outcomes. These activities help learners practice problematic sounds in a meaningful and enjoyable context.

Third, **listening to authentic spoken English** (e.g., native speakers through audio, video, and media) plays a crucial role in improving learners' pronunciation. Exposure to natural speech patterns helps students develop better awareness of stress, rhythm, and intonation.

Fourth, the review highlights that **prosodic features (stress, rhythm, and intonation) are often more challenging for EFL learners than individual sounds**, and therefore require special instructional attention in pronunciation teaching.

Fifth, the **teacher's role and instructional approach are highly influential**. Teachers who act as facilitators and integrate pronunciation into regular language teaching contribute more effectively to learners' improvement than those who treat it as an isolated skill.

Finally, the findings suggest that the ultimate goal of pronunciation teaching is **intelligibility rather than native-like accuracy**, meaning learners should be able to communicate clearly and effectively even with a foreign accent.

Overall, the literature confirms that a combination of explicit instruction, communicative practice, and exposure to authentic input is the most effective approach to teaching English pronunciation in EFL contexts.

Conclusion

This literature review has explored a variety of effective strategies for teaching English pronunciation in EFL contexts. The findings from previous studies show that pronunciation is not merely a supporting skill but a central element of communicative competence. Despite its importance, it is still frequently underemphasized in many language classrooms.

The review identified several effective instructional techniques, including tongue twisters for improving articulation and fluency, minimal pairs for distinguishing similar sounds, listening activities for exposure to authentic pronunciation, phonetic training for understanding sound systems, and instruction in rhythm and stress to develop natural speech patterns. These strategies

collectively support learners in overcoming pronunciation difficulties influenced by their first language.

Furthermore, the study highlights that successful pronunciation teaching should focus on intelligibility rather than native-like perfection. Teachers play a crucial role as facilitators who guide learners toward clearer and more effective communication. Integrating pronunciation instruction into regular language teaching, rather than treating it as an isolated component, can significantly improve learners' speaking ability.

In conclusion, effective pronunciation teaching requires a balanced approach that combines explicit instruction, meaningful practice, and consistent exposure to spoken English. By applying these strategies, EFL teachers can help learners develop clearer, more confident, and more effective oral communication skills.

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Conflict of Interests

We declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this review paper entitled “A Review On Effective Strategies for Teaching English Pronunciation to EFL learners” This study was conducted independently, and no financial, personal, or professional relationships influenced the design, analysis, interpretation, or reporting of the research findings. No external funding was received, and there were no affiliations or circumstances that could be perceived as a potential conflict of interest. We affirm that all ethical standards and academic integrity principles were strictly observed throughout the research process.

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